

Microwave assisted synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones and its 5-arylidene derivatives : Screening of antimicrobial activity with various microorganisms

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Manuscript received 06 April 2010, revised 29 December 2010, accepted 30 December 2010

Abstract : Several new ethyl(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetate (1), 2-(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetohydrazide (2), 2-(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetylhydrazino arylidenes (3a-j), 2-aryl-3-[(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetamido]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidines (4a-j) and 5-arylidene-2-aryl-3-[(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetamido]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidines (5a-j) have been synthesized. The structures of all the newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, FAB-Mass spectra and by microanalytical data. Compounds 4a-j and 5a-j have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against some selected microorganisms.

Keywords : Isonicotinamide, thiazolidinone, microwave synthesis, antimicrobial agents.

Introduction

Pyridine, a heterocyclic nucleus played a vital role in the development of different medicinal agents and in the field of agrochemicals. Pyridine and its derivatives possess various types of biological activities such as pesticidal¹, insecticidal², anticonvulsant³ and antimicrobial^{4,5}. 4-Oxo-thiazolidine derivatives also exhibit antibacterial⁶, antitubercular⁷⁻⁹, antiviral¹⁰⁻¹² and anticancer^{13,14} properties. The incorporation of 4-oxo-thiazolidine moiety in isonicotinamide through acetamidyl framework has been found to enhance the activity.

Microwave assisted heterocyclic synthesis is an efficient and eco-friendly synthetic strategy and has now become a powerful tool for green chemistry. In the recent decades, microwave heating has taken an incontestable place in organic laboratories practices as very effective and non-polluting method of activation in comparison to traditional organic synthesis involving heating by conventional methods. Microwave irradiation has been applied to organic reactions in the absence of solvent and/or in the presence of a solid support, such as clays, alumina and silica, resulting in shorter reaction times and better product yields than those obtained by using conventional

heating¹⁵⁻²¹. In the light of these observations this prompted us to synthesize a new series of isonicotinamide derivatives by incorporation the thiazolidine moiety. The structures of all compounds have been confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral analysis (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and FAB-Mass). Compounds 4a-j and 5a-j have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Results and discussion

Isonicotinamide on reaction with ethyl chloroacetate yielded ethyl(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetate (1) which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate yielded 2-(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetohydrazide (2). The condensation of compound 2 with different aromatic aldehydes afforded a series of 2-(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetylhydrazino arylidenes (3a-j). The compounds 3a-j on reaction with thioglycolic acid in the presence of anhydrous ZnCl₂ yielded 2-aryl-3-[(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetamido]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidines (4a-j). The compounds 4a-j reacted with different aromatic aldehydes in the presence of C₂H₅ONa and yielded the final products 5-arylidene-2-aryl-3-[(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetamido]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidines (5a-j) (Scheme 1). The structures of all the synthesized compounds have been

Scheme 1

elucidated on the basis of their spectral and microanalytical data.

Antimicrobial activity : Compounds **4a-j** and **5a-j** were screened for their antibacterial activity against gram-positive bacterium i.e. *Bacillus subtilis* and gram-negative bacteria i.e. *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi* using Nutrient agar medium and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium citrinum* and *Fusarium oxysporum* using Potato dextrose agar medium at 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentrations by filter paper disk technique²¹. Standard antibacterial Streptomycin and antifungal Griseofulvin were also tested under the similar conditions for comparison. The results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

From the antimicrobial studies we concluded that all compounds showed considerable and varied activity against the pathogenic bacteria and fungi. The compound **4g** showed the maximum antibacterial activity against the *E. coli* and antifungal activity against *F. oxysporum* which may be attributed to the aromatic ring and nitro group. Compounds **4c**, **4f**, **5c**, **5f** and **5g** have shown significant

antimicrobial activity, while compounds **4a**, **4b**, **4d**, **4e**, **5a**, **5b**, **5d** and **5e** have shown good antimicrobial activity and rest of the compounds have shown moderate activity. However, the activities of the synthesized compounds are less than that of standard antibacterial and antifungal drugs.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillary tubes. Formation of the compounds was routinely checked by TLC using silica gel 'G' and the spots were exposed to iodine vapours for visualization. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded at 300 MHz and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at 100 MHz on Bruker DRX-300 in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard on δ scale. The FAB-Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol SX 102 mass spectrometer. Microwave assisted reactions were carried out in Microwave oven (Bajaj 2100 ETC, 800 W, 2450 MHz). All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N percentage within the experimental limit.

Note

Table 1. Characterization data of the compounds 3b-j, 4b-j and 5b-j

Compd.	Ar	Time (min)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. formula	Found (Calcd.) (%)		
						C	H	N
3b	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2	79	170–172	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	56.81 (56.85)	4.07 (4.10)	17.66 (17.69)
3c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3	83	168–169	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	56.82 (56.85)	4.06 (4.10)	17.65 (17.69)
3d	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	2	85	150–151	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Br	49.81 (49.84)	3.56 (3.60)	15.48 (15.51)
3e	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	2	86	153–154	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Br	49.80 (49.84)	3.57 (3.60)	15.47 (15.51)
3f	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	1	90	156–157	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	54.98 (55.02)	3.93 (3.97)	21.36 (21.40)
3g	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	93	159–160	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	54.99 (55.02)	3.94 (3.97)	21.37 (21.40)
3h	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	3	82	130–131	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃	61.48 (61.51)	5.10 (5.13)	17.91 (17.94)
3i	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	2	78	135–136	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	64.81 (64.84)	5.36 (5.40)	18.88 (18.91)
3j	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	1	90	132–134	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂	62.70 (62.74)	5.81 (5.84)	21.49 (21.53)
4b	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2	84	155–156	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	52.20 (52.22)	3.81 (3.84)	14.31 (14.33)
4c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3	88	152–153	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	52.18 (52.22)	3.80 (3.84)	14.30 (14.33)
4d	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	2.5	86	142–143	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	46.84 (46.88)	3.41 (3.45)	12.83 (12.87)
4e	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	2	87	136–137	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	46.85 (46.88)	3.40 (3.45)	12.82 (12.87)
4f	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	89	147–148	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	50.83 (50.86)	3.70 (3.74)	17.41 (17.45)
4g	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	1.5	90	144–145	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	50.82 (50.86)	3.71 (3.74)	17.42 (17.45)
4h	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	1.5	80	119–120	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	55.91 (55.94)	4.62 (4.66)	14.47 (14.50)
4i	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	3	83	115–116	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S	58.33 (58.36)	4.82 (4.86)	15.10 (15.13)
4j	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	85	125–126	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃ S	57.09 (57.12)	5.22 (5.26)	17.51 (17.54)
5b	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2	85	149–150	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ SCl ₂	56.11 (56.13)	3.49 (3.51)	10.89 (10.91)
5c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	1.5	88	153–154	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ SCl ₂	56.10 (56.13)	3.47 (3.51)	10.88 (10.91)
5d	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	1.5	86	138–140	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ SBr ₂	47.79 (47.83)	2.95 (2.99)	9.26 (9.30)
5e	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	1.5	87	144–145	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ SBr ₂	47.80 (47.83)	2.94 (2.99)	9.27 (9.30)

Table-1 (contd.)

5f	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	1	89	143-144	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₇ S	53.88 (53.92)	3.34 (3.37)	15.69 (15.73)
5g	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	1	90	147-148	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₇ S	53.87 (53.92)	3.33 (3.37)	15.68 (15.73)
5h	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	2	88	125-126	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	61.86 (61.89)	4.72 (4.76)	11.09 (11.11)
5i	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	2	85	190-192	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	66.02 (66.08)	5.04 (5.08)	11.83 (11.86)
5j	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	84	121-122	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₃ S	63.33 (63.38)	5.62 (5.66)	15.81 (15.84)

Table 2. Antibacterial data of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>S. typhi</i>	
	50 µg ml ⁻¹	100 µg ml ⁻¹	50 µg ml ⁻¹	100 µg ml ⁻¹	50 µg ml ⁻¹	100 µg ml ⁻¹
4a	14	16	11.2	14	12	15
4b	17.8	19.8	14	16	16	18.5
4c	19	22	16	19	18	21
4d	15	18	12.2	14.8	13	16
4e	16	19	13.6	15.5	14.5	17.4
4f	22	26	18.5	22	21	25
4g	24	28	20	24	23	27
4h	13.2	15.5	9	12.5	10	13
4i	11	13.8	6	9.1	7	11
4j	12	14.7	8	10	9	12
5a	12.1	16	9	12.2	9.9	13
5b	15	18.8	12.5	15.2	14	17.3
5c	17	20.3	14	17.5	16	19.4
5d	13.5	17	10	13.2	10.8	14
5e	14	17.9	11.5	14.2	12.7	15.4
5f	20	24.1	16	19.8	18.5	22
5g	23	27	17.5	22	20.1	24
5h	11.5	14.2	7.5	10.3	9	11.1
5i	9.5	12	5	8.1	6.2	9
5j	10.3	13	6.3	9	7.5	10
SM ^a	26	30	23	27	25	28

^aStreptomycin, zone of inhibition in mm.

Table 3. Antifungal data of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd.	<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>P. citrinum</i>		<i>F. oxysporum</i>	
	50 µg ml ⁻¹	100 µg ml ⁻¹	50 µg ml ⁻¹	100 µg ml ⁻¹	50 µg ml ⁻¹	100 µg ml ⁻¹
4a	13	15.8	10	14	14.5	18.4
4b	17	20	15	18	17.4	21
4c	18	22	17	20.2	19.6	23
4d	14	17	12.6	14.8	15	19
4e	15	18	13.3	15.4	16	20
4f	23	25	19	21.8	22	26

Note

Table-3 (contd.)

4g	24.8	27.2	21.5	24	24	29.5
4h	12	15	9.5	12.5	13.2	17
4i	9	12	7	11	11	14
4j	11	13.5	8.8	11.8	12	16
5a	11	14	9	12.4	12.3	16
5b	16.1	19	14	17.1	16.9	19.8
5c	17	20.5	15.9	18.8	18.4	21.5
5d	12.5	15.6	11	13.9	13.7	17
5e	13.4	16.6	12.1	14.4	14.5	18
5f	21	24	17	20	22	25.5
5g	22	25	19	22.1	23.1	27
5h	10	13.8	8.3	11.3	11.4	15
5i	7.5	10.6	6	7.3	9	12.4
5j	8.3	11.4	7.2	10.2	10	13.1
GR ^a	27	30	25	28	28	32

^aGriseofulvin, zone of inhibition in mm.

Ethyl(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetate (1) : A mixture of isonicotinamide (30 g, 0.24 mol), anhydrous potassium carbonate (33.95 g, 0.24 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (30.10 g, 0.24 mol) was taken in 250 ml beaker, mixed well and irradiated in microwave oven at 800 W for 2 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction the beaker was removed from the oven and the mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature. The product was recrystallized from methanol to furnish compound 1. Yield 85%; m.p. 130–131 °C; IR (ν, cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3047 (aromatic ring), 1725 (>C=O, ester), 1638 (>C=O, amide), 1600 (>C=N), 1435 (N-CH₂); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.01 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz, CONH), 7.26–8.20 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.21 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 2.47 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 1.23 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 168.5 (>C=O, ester), 167.32 (>C=O, amide), 150.68, 150.18 (C near N of pyridine ring), 121.80, 121.62 and 121.30 (C of pyridine ring), 61.1 (COOCH₂CH₃), 39.26 (N-CH₂), 14.5 (COOCH₂CH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 208 [M⁺], 163, 135, 130, 121, 106, 102, 87, 78, 73 (Found : C, 57.63; H, 5.72; N, 13.41. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₃ : C, 57.66; H, 5.76; N, 13.45%).

2-(Isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetohydrazide (2) : A mixture of compound 1 (27 g, 0.13 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (6.49 g, 0.13 mol) was taken in 250 ml beaker, mixed well and irradiated in microwave oven at 800 W for 3 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by

TLC. After completion of the reaction the beaker was removed from the oven and the mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature. The product was recrystallized from methanol to furnish compound 2. Yield 89%; m.p. 125–127 °C; IR (ν, cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3313, 3277 (-NHNH₂), 3049 (aromatic ring), 1662, 1640 (>C=O, amide), 1602 (>C=N), 1437 (N-CH₂); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.50 (1H, s, CONH), 8.02 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz, CONH), 7.28–8.22 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.45 (2H, s, NH₂), 2.49 (2H, s, N-CH₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 170.10, 167.34 (CONH), 150.70, 150.19 (C near N of pyridine ring), 121.81, 121.62 and 121.32 (C of pyridine ring), 39.28 (N-CH₂); Mass (*m/z*) : 194 [M⁺], 178, 163, 135, 121, 116, 106, 88, 78, 73 (Found : C, 49.42; H, 5.13; N, 28.81. Calcd. for C₈H₁₀N₄O₂ : C, 49.45; H, 5.15 ; N, 28.85%).

2-(Isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetylhydrazino benzylidene (3a) : A mixture of the compound 2 (1.5 g, 0.008 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.82 g, 0.008 mol) was taken in 250 ml beaker, mixed well and irradiated in microwave oven at 800 W for 2 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction the beaker was removed from the oven and the mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature. The product was recrystallized from chloroform to furnish compound 3a. Yield 86%; m.p. 140–142 °C; IR (ν, cm⁻¹, KBr) : 3051 (aromatic ring), 1664, 1639 (>C=O, amide), 1622 (N=CH-), 1604 (>C=N), 1436 (N-CH₂); ¹H NMR (300

MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.80 (1H, s, N=CH-), 8.52 (1H, s, CONH), 8.03 (1H, t, J 6 Hz, CONH), 7.27–8.21 (9H, m, Ar-H), 2.48 (2H, s, N- CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 170.12, 167.33 (CONH), 150.69, 150.20 (C near N of pyridine ring), 142.8 (N=CH-Ar), 128.04–132.45 (C of aromatic ring), 121.83, 121.60 and 121.31 (C of pyridine ring), 39.27 (N- CH_2); Mass (m/z) : 282 [M^+], 204, 178, 176, 163, 161, 147, 135, 121, 119, 106, 104, 78 (Found : C, 63.76; H, 4.91; N, 19.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 63.80; H, 4.96; N, 19.85%).

Other compounds **3b-j** were prepared similarly by treating **2** with various aromatic aldehydes. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-3-[(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetamido]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidine (4a) : A mixture of the compound **3a** (1.2 g, 0.004 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.39 g, 0.004 mol) with a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl_2 was taken in 250 ml beaker, mixed well and irradiated in microwave oven at 800 W for 3 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction the beaker was removed from the oven and the mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature. The product was recrystallized from acetone to furnish compound **4a**. Yield 88%; m.p. 138–139 °C; IR (ν , cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3058 (aromatic ring), 2980 (N-CH-S), 1710 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, cyclic), 1673, 1650 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, amide), 1612 ($>\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1448 (N- CH_2), 690 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.61 (1H, s, CONH), 8.14 (1H, t, J 6 Hz, CONH), 7.40–8.34 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.10 (1H, s, -N-CH-), 3.11 (2H, s, COCH_2S), 2.59 (2H, s, N- CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 172.1 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, cyclic), 170.22, 167.44 (CONH), 150.79, 150.29 (C near N of pyridine ring), 128.15–132.56 (C of aromatic ring), 121.93, 121.75 and 121.43 (C of pyridine ring), 43.1 (COCH_2S), 41.1 (NCHS), 39.39 (N- CH_2); Mass (m/z) : 356 [M^+], 328, 314, 278, 250, 236, 235, 221, 208, 193, 179, 178, 163, 151, 150, 136, 135, 121, 106, 78 (Found : C, 57.26; H, 4.47; N, 15.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 57.28; H, 4.49; N, 15.72%).

Other compounds **4b-j** were prepared similarly by using **3b-j** respectively. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

5-Benzylidene-2-phenyl-3-[(isonicotinamid-4-yl)acetamido]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidine (5a) : A mixture of the compound **4a** (1 g, 0.003 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.30

g, 0.003 mol) in the presence of sodium ethoxide was taken in 250 ml beaker, mixed well and irradiated in microwave oven at 800 W for 2 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC.

After completion of the reaction the beaker was removed from the oven and the mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature. The product was recrystallized from acetone to furnish compound **5a**. Yield 85%; m.p. 132–134 °C; IR (ν , cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3065 (aromatic ring), 2987 (N-CH-S), 1713 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, cyclic), 1680, 1655 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, amide), 1630 ($>\text{C}=\text{CH-Ar}$), 1610 ($>\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1450 (N- CH_2), 692 (C-S-C); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.63 (1H, s, CONH), 8.15 (1H, t, J 6 Hz, CONH), 7.45–8.36 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.12 (1H, s, $>\text{C}=\text{CH-Ar}$), 4.14 (1H, s, -N-CH-), 2.60 (2H, s, N- CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 172.2 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, cyclic), 170.20, 167.40 (CONH), 150.90, 150.41 (C near N of pyridine ring), 129.1, 125.2 ($>\text{C}=\text{CH-Ar}$), 128.20–132.61 (C of aromatic ring), 121.85, 121.60 and 121.40 (C of pyridine ring), 41.5 (NCHS), 39.40 (N- CH_2); Mass (m/z) : 444 [M^+], 416, 366, 338, 323, 314, 309, 281, 266, 238, 236, 208, 193, 179, 178, 163, 151, 136, 135, 121, 106, 78 (Found : C, 64.80; H, 4.47; N, 12.59. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 64.84; H, 4.50; N, 12.61%).

Other compounds **5b-j** were prepared similarly by treating **4b-j** with various aromatic aldehydes. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have developed a simple and efficient method for the synthesis of 4-oxo-thiazolidines and its 5-arylidene derivatives having a isonicotinamide nucleus. We have used microwave irradiation technique. This is a solvent free reaction that leads to considerable saving in the reaction time and energetically profitable. The solvent free condition contributes to saving in cost and diminishes the waste disposal problem. Some of the synthesized compounds have shown significant antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow (India) for providing the spectral and analytical data of the compounds. Authors are also thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry for providing the laboratory

facility and Head, Department of Botany and Ms. Supriya Gupta for biological screening. One of the author (A. Upadhyay) is also grateful to UGC, New Delhi (India) for the award of UGC Meritorious Research Fellowship.

References

1. A. D. Kennedy and A. L. Summers, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1981, **18**, 409.
2. B. S. Holla, C. S. Prasanna, B. Poojary, K. S. Rao, K. Shridhara and U. G. Bhat, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 864.
3. A. Kshirsagar, M. P. Turaskar, V. M. Kulkarni, S. Dhanashire and V. Kadam, *International J. of Chem. Tech. Research*, 2009, **1**, 696.
4. N. Arikani, D. Sumengen and B. Dulger, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2008, **32**, 147.
5. R. Sharma, D. P. Nagda and G. L. Talesara, *Arkivoc*, 2006, **1**, 1.
6. C. G. Bonde and N. J. Gaikwad, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 2151.
7. N. Karali, A. Giirsoy, F. Kandemirli, N. Shvets, F. B. Kaynak, S. Ozbey, V. Kovalishyn and A. Dimoglo, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 5888.
8. S. G. Kiiciikgiizel, E. E. Oruc, S. Rollas, F. Sahin and A. Ozbek, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **37**, 197.
9. S. G. Kiiciikgiizel, A. Kocatepe, E. De Clercq, F. Sahin and M. Gilliice, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **41**, 353.
10. M. L. Barreca, J. Balzarini, A. Chimirri, E. De Clercq, L. De Luca, H. D. Holtje, M. Holtje, A. M. Monforte, P. Monforte, C. Pannecouque, A. Rao and M. Zappala, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **45**, 5410.
11. N. Kaushik-Basu, A. Bopda-Waffo, T. T. Talele, A. Basu, Y. Chen and S. G. Kiiciikgiizel, *Frontiers in Bio-science*, 2008, **13**, 3857.
12. R. Rawal, R. Tripathi, S. B. Katti, C. Pannecouque and E. De Clercq, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 1725.
13. R. Ottana, S. Carotti, R. Maccari, I. Landini, G. Chiricosta, B. Caciagli, M. G. Vigorita and E. Mini, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2005, **15**, 3930.
14. V. Gududuru, E. Hurh, J. T. Dalton and D. D. Miller, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **48**, 2584.
15. S. Caddick, *Tetrahedron*, 1995, **51**, 10403.
16. L. Perreux and A. Loupy, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 9199.
17. S. A. Galema, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1997, **26**, 233.
18. P. Lidstrom, J. Tierney, B. Wathey and J. Westman, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 9225.
19. A. R. Katritzky and S. K. Singh, *Arkivoc*, 2003, **13**, 68.
20. V. M. Patel and K. R. Desai, *Arkivoc*, 2004, **1**, 123.
21. S. K. Srivastava, A. Nema and S. D. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, **47**, 606.

